

Fish Protein Fertilizer Effect & Function in Agriculture

Fish protein organic liquid fertilizer is a pure natural fertilizer, It's rich in organic matter, fish protein, peptides, biological polysaccharides, etc. It's also a kind of functional fertilizer, can be used as base fertilizer, topdressing, can be irrigated root, drip irrigation, flushing spray. Fish protein fertilizer with rich organic matter, protein, polypeptide, etc., after plowing soil significantly increased the content of soil organic matter, can rapidly promote the soil microbial breeding, greatly activate the soil nutrient, increase the soil fertility, improve soil protecting fertilizer water retention capacity, the use of fish protein fertilizer can effectively improve soil harden problems, maintain soil fertility.

Use [fish protein](#) can promote root development, improve photosynthesis, promote the growth of plants, and is beneficial to flower bud differentiation, mature early, and can greatly improve the quality. Spraying fruit trees, the leaves green glow, disease reduction, increase the fruit and vegetable quality & yield, Fish protein fertilizer is a pollution-free environment-friendly green fertilizer nutrient.

Fish Protein Fertilizer also has a very good inhibitory effect on plant diseases and insect pests, it can be used in the following aspects: cultivating strong seedling, stimulate the potential of plants.

The Specific Application of Fish Protein in Crops

1. Tomato

In the early stage: spraying fish protein, promote leaf hypertrophy, developed roots, Improve seedling adaptability.

Bud stage: with fish protein, reduce malformed flowers, increase the fruit rate.

Expansion period: use fish protein 2 times, fruit size uniformity, increase the weight of single fruit, enhance the intensity of photosynthesis, can make the picking period extended.

2.Strawberry

After transplanting, with fish protein, slow seedling speed, good root development.

Early flowering, spraying fish protein, can increase the yield, improve the sugar content of the fruit.

3.Grapes

Spray before germination to prevent the cold spring.

Spraying fish protein 1500 times thinner after germination can speed up the growth and improve the resistance to abnormal weather.

After fruiting, spray fish protein 3 times, promote photosynthesis, improve grape sugar content, increase the weight of single ear, improve plant stress resistance.

4.Watermelon

(1) Spraying fish protein at the seedling stage, watermelon has developed roots, strong stems, slow seedling speed, reduce the occurrence of viral diseases, and improve crop stress resistance.

After sitting melon, spray fish protein 2-3 times, interval 7-14 days, enhance photosynthesis, increase yield, increase the sugar content.

5.Chili

After transplanting: spray 1500-2000 times of fish protein, spray 2-3 times, every interval of 7-15 days, improve disease resistance, reduce falling flowers and fruits, extend the harvest period, mature live culm, increase the yield of pepper, improve the quality of pepper.